

WAYS TO INCREASE THE COMPETITIVENESS OF CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS BASED ON MARKETING RESEARCH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7752042>

ELSEVIER

Received: 19-03-2023
Accepted: 20-03-2023
Published: 22-03-2023

B.K. Abdusamatov

Associate Professor of Sam DAQU "Construction Economics and Management" Department.

F.M.Rakhmonova

Sam DAQU is a senior teacher of the "Construction Economics and Management" department.

R.M.Egamov

Sam DAQU is a teacher of the "Construction Economics and Management" department.

Abstract: Илмий мақолада ишлаб чиқарилаётган қурилиш маҳсулотларнинг рақобатбардошлигини ошириш учун албатта маркетинг тадқиқотларини ўтказиш бугунги куннинг талабидир, халқаро бозорларда бу жараёнга эҳтиёжнинг мўъжизлиги, маҳсулотнинг рақобатбардошлигини оширишда маркетинг тадқиқотлар зарурлиги ва уни ўтказиш бўйича таклиф ва тавсиялар берилган.

Keywords: Инновация, инновацион тадбирлар, қурилиш, қурилиш маҳсулотлари, маркетинг, маркетинг тадқиқотлари, қурилиш маҳсулотларини баҳолаш, рақобатбардошлилик.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 19-03-2023
Accepted: 20-03-2023
Published: 22-03-2023

Abstract: научной статье даны рекомендации и необходимость по проведению маркетинговых исследований для повышения конкурентоспособности выпускаемой строительной продукции. Предложено как провести маркетинговых исследований для повышения конкурентоспособности строительного производства на международных рынках.

Keywords: инновации, инновационная деятельность, строительная продукция, маркетинг, маркетинговые исследования, оценка строительной продукции, конкурентоспособность..

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 19-03-2023
Accepted: 20-03-2023
Published: 22-03-2023

Abstract: The scientific article gives recommendations on the need for marketing research to improve the competitiveness of manufactured building products. Suggest how to conduct marketing research to improve the competitiveness of building products in international markets.

Keywords: innovations, innovative activity, building products, marketing, marketing research, evaluation of building products, competitiveness.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

"Further development and diversification of the structure of the construction materials industry, wide involvement of foreign investments for modernization of branch enterprises, technological and technical re-equipment and increase of its export potential, introduction of modern corporate management methods in accordance with international requirements and standards" [2]

To carry out marketing research in domestic and foreign markets according to today's demand for construction products, to determine the demand for modern construction materials and to carry out comprehensive measures - activities on the deep processing of local raw materials, to increase the production volumes and

expand the types of competitive, export-oriented construction products, as well as conducting in-depth marketing research on new types of high-quality building materials and developing programs for the development of the network in the medium and long term based on this" is set as a priority task.

Accordingly, one of the urgent tasks is to organize marketing research aimed at developing the export of construction products and increasing competitiveness, and conducting scientific research aimed at market segmentation.

Analysis of the literature on the topic: Marketing research is widely used to determine the demand for construction products and is one of the most common methods. Many scientific studies have been carried out by scientists of the world and our country on the use of marketing research in the segmentation of the construction products market.

Market analysis and its methodological aspects on the basis of conducting marketing research to increase the competitiveness of construction products are widely studied in the scientific researches of M. Porter and A. Aayker. In particular, A. Aayker explained that conducting marketing research using the method of market analysis using segmentation methods that are mainly carried out in the consumer sector [3].

In the theories of M. Porter, he conducted research on the use of marketing research analysis methods to distinguish the specific aspects of countries according to their competitive priorities and the formation of network industry [4].

V. Smid[5] and Y. Vindlar[6] carried out the first scientific studies on the use of the marketing research method in market research. These studies were the main motivation to expand the scope of marketing research conducted in market research.

In order to increase the competitiveness of construction products in our country, it is necessary to introduce a modern management system in the construction sector, to increase the volume of production, to increase the assortment of exportable products with the wide use of marketing research, to improve their quality, and to establish a new system aimed at finding new markets [7].

Also, the use of marketing research and analysis methods to study the market of construction products based on the information obtained by conducting marketing research, to identify the unique similarities of importing countries, is widely studied by the scientists of our republic.

Research methodology: Providing marketing research to determine the competitiveness of manufactured construction products, as well as objective evaluation and determining the factors affecting it, is a necessary stage for effective management of the enterprise.

Determination of the level of improvement of the competitiveness of construction products by means of a marketing survey is an assessment of the current state of the enterprise, which is the basis for comparison with the dynamics of changes in the process of its further development.

The main goal of marketing research is to choose a management strategy that allows the company to strengthen its position in international markets, to maintain its image, and to successfully implement it.

1. As a result of the organization and implementation of marketing research in construction product manufacturing enterprises:

2. there is an opportunity to study the existence of demand for construction products in the enterprise;

3. by analyzing the enterprise's economic development activities, there is an opportunity to study its strengths and weaknesses in terms of product production;

4. the enterprise will be able to develop proposals and recommendations for choosing a future economic development strategy and forming mechanisms for its implementation.

Analysis and results: In our scientific research work on ensuring the social and economic development of manufacturing enterprises, the existing organizational and economic mechanisms of management and the use of marketing research in the management process are of great importance.

In determining the competitiveness of manufactured construction products, it is evaluated based on the results of marketing research conducted on the basis of the opinions expressed by qualified and relevant experts of construction enterprises in Samarkand region.

There are two main things to focus on when conducting an expert evaluation effectively. The first thing to do is to create a survey, to choose the right questions to include in it, and the second is to choose the right respondents during the survey. Taking these into account, the questionnaire is developed by the author, and in the process of its formation, the opinions and opinions of experts who have worked in the field for a long time and have high experience were also taken into account.

There are two main things to focus on when conducting an expert evaluation effectively. The first thing to do is to create a survey, to choose the right questions to include in it, and the second is to choose the right respondents during the survey. Taking these into account, the questionnaire is developed by the author, and in the process of its formation, the opinions and opinions of experts who have worked in the field for a long time and have high experience were also taken into account.

According to this criterion, the respondents are also divided into 3 groups, and a significant share can be occupied by highly educated representatives who conduct scientific research in the field of management, and at the same time directly participate. The reason is that they have the potential to deeply analyze the management process both theoretically and practically, besides, they are familiar with innovative management and modern organizational and economic mechanisms of management.

At this point, we can emphasize that the acquisition of representatives of construction companies, dealers selling construction products served to better study the existing management system and problems.

The results of the expert survey are presented based on the conclusions obtained as a result of the analysis of the database formed and processed based on the results of the survey.

The respondents' conclusion on the factors affecting the improvement of the management strategy of the construction products manufacturing enterprise is studied, and an attempt was made to study the problems affecting the improvement of the production strategy and their elimination (Table 1).

τ/p	What factors affect the improvement of the strategy for the production of construction products (you can indicate several options)	(%)
1	legislative and regulatory documents related to the development of the industry; innovation policy in the field;	
2	management of product quality and competitiveness, pricing and payment policy;	
3	teaching market participants the basics of marketing;	
4	determination of market capacity by types of construction products;	
5	regular and systematic study of market systems;	
6	an effective mechanism for the production of construction products and their quality improvement	
7	changes in the domestic and world markets, inflationary processes	
8	economic policy of the state	
9	natural, geographical and ecological situation	
10	infrastructure development	
11	sources of technology acquisition	

Today, in the conditions of modernization of the economy, enterprises producing construction products can express their opinions on the main difficulties in entering the international markets of the construction products they produce and the introduction of new construction products in the enterprise (Table 2).

τ/p	What are the main difficulties in entering the international markets of the construction products produced by the construction products company	%
1	that the construction products market is not well analyzed	
2	inadequacy of marketing research performance measures	
3	overspending	

4	actions of competitors	
5	the shortcomings of the support mechanism for bringing products to the market	
6	various production problems in the production of products in enterprises and organizations	

5. In addition:

6. in the conditions of modernization and devirtification of the economy, to study the opinions of experts about the appropriateness of the process of transition to effective management of the enterprise, which factors should be used as a basis for choosing the target market for the use of marketing research in the enterprise;

7. the opinions given by the respondents on the priority level of use of raw material resources and technological capabilities in the network by construction product manufacturing enterprises;

8. the opinions of the respondents to the questionnaire about how you rate the qualifications of employees in enterprises producing building materials;

9. the opinions of the respondents to the survey on what are the necessary measures to increase the efficiency of the use of resources and technologies in construction product manufacturing enterprises;

10. the opinions given by the respondents about the prices set for the products produced in construction product manufacturing enterprises;

11. the opinions of the respondents on the marketing research conducted in order to study the quality level of the products produced in construction product manufacturing enterprises;

the opinions given by the respondents on improving the qualification of employees and improving the quality of products in the management process for the proper organization of enterprise production.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the demand for construction products is increasing while the construction sector and network are developing. In view of this, we believe that it is necessary to study the opinions of the respondents about the advantages of foreign construction products over local construction products.

Studying the opinions of the respondents about the customer service of the construction materials manufacturing enterprises also has its place in the development of the enterprise, taking this into account, we believe that it is necessary to take this process into account when conducting marketing research.

Conclusions and suggestions: It is recommended to expand the practice of using analytical grouping methods in different directions in order to identify opportunities for conducting marketing research to increase the competitiveness of construction products. Conducting and analyzing marketing research involves the classification of variables based on certain characteristics that are compatible with

each other. Based on this method, it is desirable to expand the scope of research on segmentation in marketing.

In the effective mastering of global markets, the use of analytical methods increases the effectiveness of marketing research.

From the results of the analysis based on the above data, it is clear that there are untapped market segments for enterprises producing building materials. Given that secondary data is mainly used for the purposes of setting marketing problems, we believe that increasing the competitiveness of construction products based on marketing research is one of the main foundations.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Source: <http://www.globalconstruction2030.com>
2. Decision PQ-4198 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures of fundamental improvement and comprehensive development of the construction materials industry" February 20, 2019.
3. Malhotra Neresh K. Marketingovy issledovaniya. M.: Williams, 2002. - 956p.
4. Michael Porter. Competitive strategy: Methodology analysis otrasley i konkurentov. © Izdanie na russkom yazyke, perevod, ofromlenie. LLC "Alpina Publisher", 2015
5. Smith, W. (1956), "Product Differentiation and Market Segmentation as Alternative Marketing Strategies," *Journal of Marketing*, 21, 3-8.
6. Wind, Y. (1978), "Issues and Advances in Segmentation Research," *Journal of Marketing Research*, 15 (August), 317str.